

VeriFish

The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns

Project Title	The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns
Project Acronym	VeriFish
Project Number	101156426
Type of project	HORIZON-CSA HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Topics	HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01
Starting date of Project	01 May 2024
Duration of the project	24 months
Website	www.verifish.info

D3.5 – VeriFish Prototype of the web & mobile App - final release

Work Package	WP3 Communication outreach campaigns & prototype media products
Task	T3.3 Prototype of the VeriFish web app
Lead author	Alessandro Petrocelli (COMMpla)
Contributors	Yannis Marketakis (FORTH)
Peer reviewers	Karl Presser, Malwina Cieřła (Premotec), Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)
Version	V1.0 - DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION
Due Date	31/03/2026
Submission Date	26/04/2026

Dissemination Level

X	PU: Public, fully open
	SEN: Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
	Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
	Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
	Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Version History

Funded by
the European Union

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	05/04/2025	Alessandro Petrocelli (COMMpla)	First complete version
0.2	15/04/2025	Alessandro Petrocelli (COMMpla)	Final version for internal review
1.0	29/04/2025	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT Services)	Proof reading and quality check, submission to the Participants portal

Keywords

Seafood sustainability, aquafood, verifiable indicators, FAIR data, nutrition information, environmental impact, social responsibility, GRSF, FishBase, QR code scanning, semantic data integration, open data, RESTful API, VeriFish Knowledge Base, cross-platform App, Flutter, React Native, data visualization, real-time updates, JSON, SPARQL queries.

Disclaimer

VeriFish offers a framework of verifiable sustainability indicators for communications about sustainability based on FAIR data from EU- and global aquafoods repositories, brought together through the extraordinary collaboration of European-wide actors. Leveraging on this indicator, VeriFish designs, develops, and disseminates a number of media products to help citizens, seafood consumers and retailers, associations and policy makers make informed consumption choices.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The VeriFish app represents a key milestone in making seafood sustainability information accessible to European consumers and stakeholders. This document presents a concise description of the final release of the VeriFish web and mobile application *D3.5 Prototype of the web app - final release - DEM*, marking the completion of the prototype development cycle initiated with *D3.2 VeriFish web app requirements & specification document* and *D3.4 Prototype of the web app - initial release*. The application is now publicly available as a web-app at the address <https://app.verifish.info/> and is being published on both the Apple App Store and Google Play Store during May 2026.

The final release builds on all core functionalities developed in the initial release -species factsheets, multilingual search, sustainability indicators, nutritional data, and provenance information- and introduces a significant architectural upgrade: the migration of the backend data layer from Firebase/Firestore to Supabase. This change was driven by the need for more expressive and flexible query capabilities, enabling richer data filtering, more efficient joins across species data, and better support for structured analytics that the application's growing data model required. This release also addresses the feedback received during the two feedback gathering sessions organised on 20 November 2025 during the VeriFish Workshop at the Catch Welfare Platform Conference 2025, and on 11 March 2026 in conjunction with the VeriFish final event (both sessions are further reported in *D3.6 Communication, stakeholder engagement final report*)

In addition, the final release introduces major enhancements to usability and performance, including a fully redesigned user interface based on expert feedback, simplified navigation, integration of new data sources such as the dataset from EU's STECF, and an expanded set of socio-economic, environmental, and aquaculture indicators' data.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction & Background	4
1.1. Links with other deliverables	4
1.2. Structure of the deliverable	4
2. Overview of the Web App Prototype	5
2.1. Technology Stack	5
2.2. Migration from Firebase to Supabase	5
2.3. Linking Verified Indicators to International Certification Schemes	6
2.4. User Experience & Features	6
2.5. Client Interaction	7
2.6. Data Workflow & Architecture	7
3. Links to the Published Version	7
4. Conclusion	11

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1 VeriFish web-app landing page search catalogue	8
Figure 2 Example of Catalogue search	9
Figure 3 Example of factsheet showcasing nutritional data	9
Figure 4 Example of factsheet showcasing socio-economic data	10
Figure 5 Example of factsheet showcasing certifications on species	10

1. Introduction & Background

The VeriFish Mobile and Web Application is a key component of the project's ambition to make sustainability information about seafood products accessible, verifiable, and actionable for European consumers. This document describes the final release of the prototype of the VeriFish web & mobile app, a mobile-friendly tool for communicating transparent information on seafood and aquaculture sustainability. It follows the initial release documented in *D3.4 Prototype of the web app - initial release*.

The final release consolidates all features developed during the prototyping phase and brings the application to a state of public readiness. The app is now fully available on the web and is in the process of being published on mobile stores, fulfilling the objectives set in T3.3 of WP3.

1.1. Links with other deliverables

This deliverable is the direct continuation of *D3.4 Prototype of the web app - initial release* and represents the completion of the development cycle defined in *D3.2 - VeriFish Web App Requirements & Specification Document* where detailed requirements, specifications, and system architecture are covered. It integrates the indicator framework from *D2.1 Indicator framework* defined and *D2.2 Indicator framework developed*, and relies on the data infrastructure described in *D2.4 VeriFish Knowledge Base - interim version* and its final form as presented in *D2.5 VeriFish Knowledge Base - final version*. It also constitutes the technical entry point for MS6 (Prototype of the web app - initial release), MS7 (First version of the VeriFish factsheets) and MS4 (VeriFish Knowledge Base - interim version).

1.2. Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is organised into four sections:

- Section 1: Introduction & Background - purpose, scope, and context of the final release.
- Section 2: Overview of the Final Release - technology stack (including the Supabase migration), features, and data architecture.
- Section 3: Links to the Published Version - public access details for both web and mobile.
- Section 4: Conclusions - summary of achievements and project status.

2. Overview of the Web App Prototype

The final release of the VeriFish app represents the completion of the prototype development phase. It delivers all functionalities specified in D3.2 and introduces a key architectural upgrade - the migration to Supabase¹ - that substantially strengthens the application's data layer. The full implementation details and system architecture remain as specified in *D3.2 - VeriFish Web App Requirements & Specification Document*. This section focuses on what is new or updated in the final release.

2.1. Technology Stack

- **Frontend:** Compose Multiplatform², using Kotlin Multiplatform³ with a responsive design based on Google Material Design 3 Expressive⁴
- **Backend & Data Layer: Supabase** (PostgreSQL-based), replacing Firebase/Firestore. See Section 2.2 for the migration rationale
- **Authentication:** Supabase Auth (email/password and OAuth providers), replacing Firebase Authentication
- **External APIs & Services:** VeriFish Knowledge Base (authoritative data source), OpenAI⁵, Gemini (multilingual species names, Images review and generation).

2.2. Migration from Firebase to Supabase

Species factsheets

The most significant change in the final release is the migration of the backend data layer from Firebase/Firestore to Supabase. This decision was driven by concrete technical needs that emerged during development and testing of the application.

Firebase/Firestore, as a NoSQL document store, has well-known limitations in querying: it does not natively support joins across collections, has restricted filtering capabilities on multiple fields simultaneously, and does not allow the kinds of aggregations and structured queries that the growing complexity of the VeriFish data model required. As the application evolved to incorporate multiple sustainability indicators, nutritional data across cooking methods, provenance metadata, and multilingual content, these limitations became a significant constraint.

Supabase built on PostgreSQL provides full relational query capabilities, including complex joins, aggregate functions, full-text search, and row-level security policies. This enables the app to:

¹ <https://supabase.com/>

² <https://www.jetbrains.com/compose-multiplatform/>

³ <https://kotlinlang.org/docs/multiplatform.html>

⁴ [Material Design 3 - Google's latest open source design system](#)

⁵ <https://platform.openai.com/docs/overview>

-
- Perform efficient cross-dimensional queries (e.g. filtering species by FAO area AND fishing method AND sustainability tier simultaneously).
 - Support structured data analytics and reporting for future monitoring features.
 - Manage relational data (species ↔ indicators ↔ nutritional values ↔ provenance) in a normalised schema, reducing data duplication.
 - Leverage Supabase's built-in REST and real-time API, which integrates cleanly with the Compose Multiplatform frontend.

The migration was carried out without any impact on the user-facing features of the application. All data previously managed in Firestore has been migrated and restructured in Supabase's PostgreSQL schema.

2.3. Linking Verified Indicators to International Certification Schemes

One of the key updates introduced in the latest version of the app is the integration of MSC (Marine Stewardship Council) fisheries certification data into the species and fishery factsheets. Certification status is now retrieved directly from the MSC fisheries database, allowing users to immediately verify whether a given fishery holds an active MSC certification. This addition strengthens the transparency layer of the app, connecting verified sustainability indicators with internationally recognised certification schemes and giving both consumers and producers access to a fuller, status of fishery performance.

2.4. User Experience & Features

All core features implemented in the initial release (D3.4) are present and fully operational in the final release:

- **Species factsheets:** taxonomy, images, sustainability indicators, nutritional information, provenance (FAO areas, gear/production methods), and related metadata.
- **Advanced search:** by common or scientific name, with language preferences, FAO area filters, and fishing method filters. Progressive refinement with typeahead suggestions.
- **Producer Stories:** structured submission forms for fishers and aquaculture producers, capturing first-person accounts of sustainable practices.
- **Nutritional heat map:** visualisation comparing nutritional values across different cooking methods, finalised in this release.
- **Multilingual support:** common names and UI content available across multiple European languages.

2.5. Client Interaction

From the first screen, users see a prominent search bar and key filters (language, FAO areas, methods). Search results present compact previews -scientific/common name, image, and a snapshot of key indicators. Selecting a species opens a detail page with clearly separated sections:

- **Overview** with headline indicators and resource status
- **Sustainability** with indicator details and brief methodological notes
- **Nutrition** with core nutrient values and references
- **Provenance** with FAO areas, gear/production method, and metadata
- **Media** with images and, where available, linked Producer Stories

The UI emphasises consistency and accessibility with responsive layout to work smoothly across desktop, tablet, and smartphone. The experience is tailored to different audiences of citizens.

2.6. Data Workflow & Architecture

Data pipelines have been fully migrated and optimised for the Supabase backend:

- **Authoritative ingest from the VeriFish Knowledge Base:** species lists and identifiers are pulled via the KB API and stored in Supabase, with relational links to indicator and nutritional tables.
- **Media enrichment:** AI queries for species images remain unchanged, with results persisted in Supabase storage.
- **Multilingual naming:** OpenAI-assisted generation of common names across European languages, now stored in a dedicated multilingual names table in Supabase.
- **Species image:** Starting from FAO's legacy black-and-white hand-drawn species illustrations, we used Gemini to produce enhanced, colorised, and higher-quality versions, now integrated into the platform.
- **Real-time and caching:** Supabase's built-in real-time subscriptions and connection pooling replace the Firestore caching layer, providing low-latency responses for the UI.

3. Links to the Published Version

The final release of the VeriFish app is publicly available. Till 30 April 2026, the web-app link was accessible upon request by users via a webform from the VeriFish website. Once received the request, an email was sent to each user with the password to access the prototype of the web-app, that was still in protection mode. The password protection applied in the initial release has now been removed, and the application is now openly accessible to all users.

The web version of the app is publicly accessible at: <https://app.verifish.info/>

The VeriFish mobile application is being published on both major mobile stores during April 2026 and will be available for public download by end of month

iOS (Apple devices)

- The app will be publicly available on the Apple App Store for download by any iOS user, without requiring TestFlight or an invitation.

Android devices

- The app will be publicly available on the Google Play Store for download by any Android user.

Store links will be made available on the VeriFish website at <https://verifish.info/verifish-web-app/> as soon as the listings are approved and live.

Figure 1 VeriFish web-app landing page search catalogue

Figure 2 Example of Catalogue search

Figure 3 Example of factsheet showcasing nutritional data

Figure 4 Example of factsheet showcasing socio-economic data

Figure 5 Example of factsheet showcasing certifications on species

4. Conclusion

The completion of D3.5 marks the end of the VeriFish application prototype development phase. The final release delivers a fully functional, publicly accessible web and mobile application that integrates verifiable sustainability, nutritional, and provenance data for aquafood species into an intuitive, multilingual interface.

This release introduces substantial improvements across the entire application, significantly enhancing both functionality and user experience. Following expert feedback, the user interface has been completely redesigned to maximize simplicity and usability, removing unnecessary filters and making navigation more intuitive for end users. The platform now integrates additional data sources, including STECF, and expands its analytical capabilities with a broader set of socio-economic and environmental indicators, as well as newly incorporated aquaculture data.

Performance has also been significantly optimized, reducing loading times and delivering a smoother and more responsive user experience. In this context, the migration from Firebase to Supabase represents an important technical upgrade, resolving previous query limitations and enabling more advanced data operations such as multi-dimensional filtering, structured analytics, and richer indicator integrations.